

FISCAL ECONOMICS

RESEARCH TITLE: Optimization of a Stock Portfolio, to potentially Increase Returns and Decrease
the Risk of Investment

17/09/2022

EXPLORATION

Introduction :

I have chosen to analyze the stock market trend of Bitcoin from the 28th of December 2021 to 13th January 2022. I will be basing my research on the continuous increment curve, found in between the aforementioned dates. Choosing to study the 17 dates where there was a continuous increase in bitcoin's price, the aim of my study is to make effective use of multiple mathematical techniques to graphically visualize and model the growth and decay of Bitcoin's stock price. After the graphical representation of the same, I will then analyze its behavior in relation to the cryptocurrency's major investor MicroStrategy Incorporated to see how much BTC is dependent on MSTR, and I will be using differentiation to model the growth and decay of the stock price. This will help me determine the rate of change in stock price value over the selected period. Using standard deviation, variance, covariance, and the Pearson's correlation coefficient, I will analyze the volatile changes in stock values, which will help me assess the risks associated with investing in Bitcoin, and how the market may respond to changes in Bitcoin's stock price. I will use polynomial functions to model the growth pattern of the stock. To analyze the relationship between the stock price, and the difference between the price on day 'z' and day 'z+1', I will use regression analysis. By comparing the data from these functions, I will be able to determine the level of correlation between the rise in MSTR's stock price from day 1 to 17, and BTCs stock price from day 1 to 17, as well as the impact of company earnings on the stock price, where using the 'r value' that will represent how much correlation there is, in the two variables. Finally, I will use the results of the previous

analyses to identify the factors that contribute to the growth and decay of the Bitcoin stock price. This will help me to make predictions about the future behavior of the Bitcoin stock price. In conclusion, my math IA will provide a comprehensive analysis of the Bitcoin stock market trend using a variety of mathematical techniques. By exploring the relationships between the stock price, market trends, and company earnings, I hope to provide valuable insights into the behavior of the Bitcoin stock price and the risks associated with investing in Bitcoin as compared to other assets.

Table 1 - BTC Value from 28/12/2021 to 12/1/2022¹

Serial Number	Dates	BTC Value (\$)
1.	28/12/2021	16552.57
2.	29/12/2021	16642.34
3.	30/12/2021	16602.59
4.	31/12/2021	16547.50
5.	01/01/2022	16625.08
6.	02/01/2022	16688.47
7.	03/01/2022	16679.86
8.	04/01/2022	16836.74
9.	05/01/2022	16951.97
10.	06/01/2022	16955.08

¹ Finance, Yahoo. "Bitcoin USD (BTC-USD) Price History & Historical Data – Yahoo Finance." *Yahoo! Finance*, Yahoo!, sg.finance.yahoo.com/quote/BTC-USD/history/. Date Accessed 29 March 2023

11.	07/01/2022	17091.14
12.	08/01/2022	17196.55
13.	09/01/2022	17446.29
14.	10/01/2022	17934.9
15.	11/01/2022	18869.59
16.	12/01/2022	19909.57
17.	13/01/2022	20976.30

Rate of Change using Algebra -

To find the rate of change using calculus, we have to use the derivative of the function that generates these values. Since we only have a set of data points, we cannot know the exact function that generated them, but we can estimate it using a curve fitting method, such as linear regression. We could use Linear regression, which is a method that finds the best-fitting line that minimizes the sum of the squared differences between the observed values and the predicted values.

Taking the initial value as, 16552.57 (the first data point) and the final value is 20976.30 (the last data point), and the time interval is 17 days (the total number of days), we get an average rate of change, of $(20976.30 - 16552.57) / 17 = 260.2194118$

Therefore, the average rate of change of the currency value over the entire time period is approximately 260.219 currency units per day. This represents the overall trend in the currency value over the time period, averaged out over all the fluctuations and changes that occurred during that time.

Estimation of the primary stock function -

Based on the given data in Table 1, we can create a polynomial function of degree 4, that approximates the values over time. The function would be of the form:

$$y = ax^4 + bx^3 + cx^2 + dx + e$$

where y is the value of the variable (i.e., currency), x axis represents the price of the coin from day 1 (28/12/2021) to day 17 (13/01/2022), and the y axis represents the difference between the coin on day x+1, 'e' is a constant that determines this graph's position in the y-axis, d is the coefficient of x, and is a variable that defines the function's position in the x-axis, the variable 'b' serves as a measure of how steep the graph will go (minima), 'a' determines the shape of the graph, as it is alongside x^4 and 'c' is a variable that decides how the concave of the graph is, whether it is concave up, or concave down.²

$$y = 16552.57$$

$$x = 1 \text{ (since this is the first data point)}$$

² Mali, Kavita. "Everything You Need to Know about Linear Regression!" *Analytics Vidhya*, 12 Sept. 2022, www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2021/10/everything-you-need-to-know-about-linear-regression/. Accessed on 29 March 2023

Figure 1 - Polynomial Function of degree 4, created by plotting the varying bitcoin prices over 17 days.

After creating this graph, the derived polynomial function is,

$$0.3009356890529x^{(4)} - 7.3738942142309x^{(3)} + 64.7691461756774x^{(2)} - 193.0588067264762x + 16737.063857466088$$

This function can be used to estimate the value of the variable for any given time in days. For example, to estimate the value after 30 days, we would substitute $x = 30$ and get the estimated value of the BTC.

Using Calculus,

Let's consider the given data as a function of time, where t is the time in days and C is the currency value, referring to Graph 1,

$$C(t) = \{16552.57, 16642.34, 16602.59, 16547.50, 16625.08, 16688.47, 16679.86, 16836.74, 16951.97, 16955.08, 17091.14, 17196.55, 17446.29, 17934.90, 18869.59, 19909.57, 20976.30\}$$

To find the rate of change, we need to take the derivative of this function with respect to time which means, the rate of change is simply dC/dt . Since the data points are discrete, we can use the finite difference method to approximate the derivative. The difference formula for the first derivative is:

$$dC/dt \approx [C(t + 1) - C(t)]/\Delta t$$

where Δt is the time interval between two consecutive data points (in this case, $\Delta t = 1$ day).

Using the data point, we can estimate the varying rates of change across a variety of data points.

Finding the derivative using limit,

To find the derivative of this function, we can use the concept of the limit. The derivative of $C(t)$ with respect to time, denoted by dC/dt , is given by:

$$dC/dt = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} [(C(t + \Delta t) - C(t))/\Delta t]$$

Using this formula, we can find the rate of change at each time point. For example, at the first data point ($t=1$), the rate of change is:

$$\begin{aligned} dC/dt &= \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} [(C(1 + \Delta t) - C(1))/\Delta t] \\ &= \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} [(16642.34 - 16552.57)/\Delta t] = 89.77 \end{aligned}$$

³ Haese, Michael, et al. "Mathematics: Analysis and Approaches HL." *Haese Mathematics*, Prolong Press Limited, 21 May 2021, www.haesemathematics.com/books/mathematics-analysis-and-approaches-hl. Accessed 03 April 2023

Using the method of finite differences with a time interval of 1 day, I got the following table for specific rates of change.

Serial Number	Date	Currency Change (\$)
1.	28/12/2021	89.77
2.	29/12/2021	-39.75
3.	30/12/2021	-55.09
4.	31/12/2021	78.58
5.	01/01/2021	123.39
6.	02/01/2021	-8.61
7.	03/01/2021	156.88
8.	04/01/2021	115.23
9.	05/01/2021	3.11
10.	06/01/2021	136.06
11.	07/01/2021	105.41
12.	08/01/2021	249.74
13.	09/01/2021	488.61
14.	10/01/2021	934.68

15.	11/01/2021	1039.98
16.	12/01/2021	1066.35

Table 1 - Rate of Change in BTC prices over the course of 17 days from 28/12/2021 to 13/01/2022

Standard Deviation, Variance, and Covariance -

To calculate the standard deviation, variance, and covariance for the Bitcoin price data from the table provided, we first need to calculate the mean (μ) of the prices:

$$\mu = (16552.57 + 16642.34 + 16602.59 + 16547.5\dots + 20976.3) / 17$$

$$\mu \approx 17441.55$$

Now, we can use the formulas to calculate the standard deviation, variance, and covariance:

$$\text{Standard deviation } (\sigma) = \sqrt{(\sum(x - \mu)^2 / n)}$$

$$\sigma \approx 1251.80$$

Figure 2 - Standard Deviation graph of the price of BTC, in relation to the normal distribution.

$$\text{Variance } (\sigma^2) = \Sigma(x - \mu)^2/n \approx 1567003.24$$

A variance of 1567003.24 indicates that the data is very well spread out, on the graph. Variance is generally used as a statistical measure of risk and volatility. A positive variance meaning a higher risk and a negative variance meaning lower risk, a variance of 1567003.24 indicates that there is an extremely high risk with investment of any money, at this point in time.

$$\text{cov}(x, y) = \Sigma((x - \bar{x}) \times (y - \bar{y})) / n$$

where x and y are the two variables being analyzed, $\bar{x}$ is the mean of x , $\bar{y}$ is the mean of y , and n is the number of data points. I have chosen one of bitcoin's biggest investors Microstrategy Ltd. (MSTR) to see how much interdependence is visible.

In the graph seen below, 'x' represents the market value of BTC varying everyday from 28/12/2021 to 13/01/2022, 'y' represents the market value of MSTR⁴ from 28/12/2021 to 13/01/2022.

x	y	$\bar{x}$	$\bar{y}$	$x - \bar{x}$	$y - \bar{y}$	$(x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})$
16552.57	147	17441.55	156.18	-888.98	-9.18	8160.8364
16642.34	139.9	17441.55	156.18	-799.21	-16.28	13011.1388
16602.59	133.82	17441.55	156.18	-839.05	-22.36	18761.1580
16547.50	148.67	17441.55	156.18	-894.05	-10.51	9396.4655
16625.08	0	17441.55	156.18	-816.47	-156.18	127516.284
16688.47	0	17441.55	156.18	-753.08	-156.18	117616.034
16679.86	146.8	17441.55	156.18	-761.69	-9.38	7144.6522
16836.74	160.54	17441.55	156.18	-604.81	4.36	-2636.9716
16951.97	152.61	17441.55	156.18	-489.88	-3.57	1747,8
16955.08	170	17441.55	156.18	-486.47	13.82	-6723.015
17091.14	174.35	17441.55	156.18	-350.41	18.17	-6366.9497
17196.55	189	17441.55	156.18	-245	32.82	-8040.9
17446.29	203.65	17441.55	156.18	4.74	47.47	225.0078

⁴ Finance, Yahoo`. "Microstrategy Incorporated (MSTR) Stock Historical Prices & Data." *Yahoo! Finance*, Yahoo!, finance.yahoo.com/quote/MSTR/history/. Accessed 02 April 2023

17934.9	206	17441.55	156.18	493.35	49.82	24578.697
18869.59	232	17441.55	156.18	1428.04	75.82	108273.992
19909.57	237	17441.55	156.18	2468.02	80.82	199465.37
20976.30	216.77	17441.55	156.18	3534.75	60.59	214170.5

Table 2 - Calculation of Covariance using MSTR and BTC values for $\bar{x}$ and $\bar{y}$

MSTR, or MicroStrategy, is a publicly traded software company that provides business intelligence, mobile software, and cloud-based services. The company made headlines in 2020 when it announced that it had invested a significant portion of its cash reserves in Bitcoin as a hedge against inflation. Since then, MicroStrategy has continued to invest in a lot of Bitcoin, and the value of the company's Bitcoin holdings is so high, that it actually crosses the profitability of the company by itself, that is how much bitcoin they have accumulated over the years. While MicroStrategy is a separate software company by itself, it has become closely associated with Bitcoin due to its large investment in the cryptocurrency. The relationship between MicroStrategy and Bitcoin is primarily financial, as MicroStrategy has made a significant investment in Bitcoin.⁵ I am analyzing the covariance between the Bitcoin price and MSTR stock price. So, using the above formula, I calculated the covariance as +48605.88884

Therefore, the covariance between Bitcoin prices and MSTR values is 48605.88884, indicating that as the stock prices of MSTR increases, the stock price of BTC also increases. This could be one of the most influential factors on Bitcoin's meteoric rise, from 28th of December 2021, to January the 13th 2022.

⁵ Asmakov, Andrew. "Microstrategy's Bitcoin Bet Now in Profit amid Latest Rally." *Decrypt*, Decrypt, 11 Apr. 2023, decrypt.co/125941/microstrategy-bitcoin-bet-now-profit-latest-rally.

These measures are important in understanding the volatility and correlation of the Bitcoin price with other variables, as it helps the reader understand how much risk there is, in being associated with investing in Bitcoin, because the market is always unstable and very volatile. For example, a higher standard deviation indicates that the price of Bitcoin is more volatile and has more frequent fluctuations over time, making it an extremely large investment filled with risk. A positive covariance with the stock prices of companies that have invested in Bitcoin indicates that these two variables tend to move in the same direction, meaning that if MSTR as a firm succeeds in its operations and responsibilities, so will BTC. If MSTR stock prices go down due to any unnamed factor, so will BTC. This is what is proven with a positive covariance. The standard deviation of a stock market data set represents the amount of volatility or prices of BTC stocks in the market. A higher standard deviation indicates that the prices of the stocks are more spread out from the average price, and therefore there is more volatility in the market. In this specific data set, the standard deviation of approximately 1251.8 currency units indicates that the currency value experienced significant fluctuations during the time period, with prices changing by thousands of units in either direction. The variance of approximately 1567003.24 (SD currency squared) indicates that these fluctuations were large in magnitude and have had a significant impact on the overall value of the currency. This suggests that periods of high volatility in the currency value may have been associated with downward pressure on the currency price.

Plotting the data, and the function of the dataset,

Referring to Figure 1,

The extremum here, shows us that on the 2nd day, after 6 AM (0.24 x day), the stock price hits its lowest at \$16554. This means that for someone looking to invest in BTC, when they calculate the graph using the older prices, it allows them to foresee the lowest point, and invest in the coin, as its value increases, to maximize the return yield, and make a large profit as a crypto investor. This would allow for the maximization of personal investment returns for the investor.

Linear Regression :

I used linear regression to determine the relationship between the Bitcoin stock price and various independent variables, in this case : time. Linear regression is a statistical method that can be used to determine the linear relationship between two or more variables. In this case, you can use linear regression to determine the relationship between the Bitcoin stock price and the market trends function and company earnings function. The 'x' axis represents the price of bitcoin from 1/1/2023, when the prices of bitcoin started skyrocketing. The 'y' axis represents the dates from New Years Day till the 13th of January, 2023, when the collected data ends.

Pearson-Correlation Coefficient :

The correlation coefficient tells us the strength and direction of the relationship between the two variables. A correlation coefficient of -1 indicates a perfectly negative linear relationship, which means

that if there is success in MSTR, there is most definitely an inverse relationship causing failure in bitcoin and vice versa. A coefficient of 0 indicates no linear relationship, and a coefficient of 1 indicates a perfectly positive linear relationship which means if there is success in MSTR, there is success in BTC and vice versa. In general, the closer the correlation coefficient is to -1 or 1, the stronger the linear relationship between the variables, while a coefficient closer to 0 indicates a weaker linear relationship. The sign of the correlation coefficient tells us the direction of the relationship. A positive coefficient indicates a positive linear relationship, where an increase in one variable is associated with an increase in the other variable. A negative coefficient indicates a negative linear relationship, where an increase in one variable is associated with a decrease in the other variable.

Next, I have calculated the Pearson's correlation coefficient using the formula:

$$\frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Using the data from Table 2 for MSTR and BTC prices, I got the r value to be

$$r = 0.8606$$

The Pearson's correlation coefficient between the two variables is 0.8606, indicating a strong positive correlation.

Limitations and Conclusion :

As a school student, I faced several limitations when it came to analyzing investments and performing market research. I didn't have access to the resources and capital required to make significant investments and had to look to secondary sources to gain monetary information. I wasn't able to seek returns like a professional investor would due to a severe lack in experience with cryptocurrency stocks and a very

weak understanding of the BTC stock trends. Additionally, I didn't have access to the kind of in-depth research and analysis technologies that larger crypto firms do and had to refer to my knowledge of mathematics to come up with an effective analysis and understanding of the agenda. In terms of the limitations of this essay, there were a few areas where my lack of expertise and resources impacted how comprehensive my analysis was. For example, I wasn't able to conduct extensive research into the global factors that impact the bitcoin market and I didn't have access to real-time data on the main reasons behind these fluctuations in the market, and had to make a prediction as to what could have made the stocks so volatile. If these limitations were non-existent, or at least lower than they are now, I believe that the essay could have been much more comprehensive and provided a more detailed analysis of the bitcoin market and its relationship to global factors like inflation, perhaps even help reduce the risk of investment in cryptocurrencies such as bitcoin. While conducting all the standard deviation tests, and analysis, I found myself often times using estimation methods to the 3 most significant figures, This limitation meant that any analysis I conducted would not be on the raw data, but instead on the rounded-off data, and hence affected the accuracy of the results seen in the essay. I would have been able to analyze market trends more effectively and provide more accurate predictions for the future of the market, in the case that I had perfect knowledge on the exact causes of this volatility in stock price. Overall, while my limitations as a student impacted the depth of my analysis, I hope that this essay still provides some valuable insights into the bitcoin market and the impact of global factors on its performance.

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